

**POLYTECHNIQUE
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Additively Manufactured Thermally Bistable Structures

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Introduction

Proposed Design

Carbon-Reinforced
Nylon

TPU 95A

Stiff Material
in walls

Soft Material

Regular non-smart materials

Collaborators
Prof. Hamid Akbarzadeh, McGill
Prof. Daniel Therriault, Poly

Mechanical Bistability Vs. Thermal Bistability

Structural stability
(Thermal and mechanical perspectives)

Mechanically Bistable

Mechanically Monostable

Thermally Bistable

Thermally Monostable

Thermally Monostable

Effect of design Features on Mechanical Bistability

Takeaways:

- Maximum force has a direct relation with: struts' angle, struts' thickness, wall thickness, number of parallel struts
- Adding a ribbon of stiff materials to the walls can turn a monostable structure to a bistable structure

Wall stiffness and Bistability Energy

- The “Equivalent wall stiffness” is obtained using cantilever composite beam theory
- There is a “Critical equivalent wall stiffness” for a design with specified strut angle and thickness
- For walls stiffer than the critical value the structure is bistable

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Wall stiffness and Bistability

Takeaways:

- The critical value for “Equivalent wall stiffness parameter” has a direct relation with strut thickness and opposite relation with strut angles
- The non-dimensional bistability energy has a direct relation with “Equivalent wall stiffness parameter” for bistable structures

Force – Displacement – Temperature

Takeaways

- According to FE results Triggering temperatures vary between 20°C to 55°C
- Force – Displacement – Temperature of the thermally bistable structure resembles shape memory alloys

Effect of design Parameters on Triggering Temperature

Takeaways

- Triggering temperature has an inverse relation with the strut thickness
- Triggering temperature has a direct relation with the wall stiffness
- Triggering temperature has an inverse relation with the bistability energy

Experimental Results

Takeaways:

- In general, FE and experiment predict same trends
- FE generally overestimates the maximum and minimum force of the bistable structures
- Experimental results for Triggering Temperature is less than FE prediction

Experimental Results

Experimental Results

Tessellated Thermally Bistable Structure

Concluding Remarks

- The proposed design paradigm enables attaining shape memory behavior without exploiting special polymers
- Unlike SMA and SMPs, the restoration of initial configuration happens in a snap-like behavior
- The triggering temperature can be tuned by changing the design parameters
- Through tessellation strategies, we can customize the response of thermally bistable structure by amplifying the deformation or tailoring the triggering temperatures
- Further research can enable us to utilize the design as self-sensing actuator since the design quickly responds to change in temperature

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